

Supplementary File 3

Detailed Framework

Assessing gene and disease eligibility for therapy development requires weighing different aspects, which we have divided into molecular, clinical, and practical considerations (**Figure 2**, main text), and briefly explained in the main manuscript. In the following sections, the different considerations for assessing the eligibility of a gene/disease for genetic intervention are addressed in more detail, providing further information, such as tools, databases, programs, and examples that can aid in the assessment. For the separate criteria, we additionally highlight the different considerations to be made for generalized and individualized therapy assessment. A full list of recommended resources to support assessment can be found in Supplement 4.

This section is structured the same as the condensed overview in the main manuscript presented in **Figure 2** (main text). The framework was applied to multiple example diseases which can be found in **Supplement 2**.

1. Molecular considerations

The first steps in evaluating a gene for genetic intervention are understanding the molecular cause of the disease, defining the gene-disease association, identifying the mechanism of disease, and gathering information on dosage sensitivity. This will ultimately allow the determination of the most suitable therapeutic approach.

1.1 Cause of the disease

1.1.1 Molecular genetic diagnosis

A critical challenge in evaluating genetic therapy eligibility remains with the ability to provide the precise molecular diagnosis. The wider utilization of next-generation sequencing (NGS) technology has revolutionized genetic diagnosis by enabling comprehensive and rapid analysis of the genome. Today, gene panels, exome sequencing, genome sequencing, and RNA sequencing have a combined diagnostic rate of about 40%.¹⁻⁶ Unlike DNA-based methods, which are largely tissue-agnostic (excepting somatic mosaicism), RNA sequencing is constrained by tissue-specific expression.⁷ Should therapy be considered for genes that are expressed in specific cell types, appropriate diagnostic methods should be consulted to help identify and diagnose patients. This also includes paying special attention to understanding where a variant is located in respect to relevant transcripts. A variant might for example be located deep in the intron in the MANE select transcript but exonic in the transcript expressed in the affected tissue, which will change the interpretation of the variant but also eligibility to potential therapeutic interventions.

A definitive genetic diagnosis is necessary before an individual can be considered for genetic interventions. For therapeutic evaluation, we generally consider it necessary to have a genetic

diagnosis of a likely pathogenic or pathogenic variant based on the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) guidelines.⁸ The identified variant should be clinically relevant, hence, a sole (likely) pathogenic variant alone that cannot fully explain the individual's phenotype should be treated with caution. In compound heterozygous cases, both variants should be (likely) pathogenic; however, one of the variants being a variant of unknown significance (VUS) can be eligible as long as the clinical presentation of the individual is consistent with the diagnosis.⁹ In other cases, it is not recommended to use a VUS for therapeutic development.

If in doubt, and wherever possible, we recommend further investigating the functional consequences of individual variants to confirm the diagnosis and the variant's impact on the disease manifestation.

1.1.2 Gene-disease association

To assess therapeutic eligibility, the gene-disease association should be understood. A gene-disease association refers to a demonstrated causative correlation between specific genetic variations in a gene and the onset, course, or progression of a defined disease (clinical presentation/symptoms). When available, gene-disease associations can be identified through curated resources such as ClinGen (<https://clinicalgenome.org/>), OMIM (<https://www.omim.org/>), Gene Reviews (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK11116/>), Orphanet (<https://www.orpha.net/>), Genotype-to-Phenotype (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gene2phenotype/>), and the PanelApp (<https://panelapp.genomicsengland.co.uk/panels/484/>), which consolidate evidence from peer-reviewed literature, expert review, and case-level data.¹⁰⁻¹⁴ However, in the context of rare or newly described conditions, these databases may lack sufficient coverage, necessitating independent evaluation of the gene-disease relationship based on scientific literature. Establishing a strong gene-disease association is a foundational requirement for assessing the feasibility of gene-targeted therapies, and it ensures that therapeutic development is grounded in causative biology rather than association alone. These gene-disease association evaluations must be conducted at the disease level, not the gene level, particularly when a single gene is implicated in multiple phenotypically and mechanistically distinct conditions. For instance, pathogenic variants in *SCN2A* may lead to epileptic encephalopathy (OMIM #613721), episodic ataxia (OMIM #618924), or benign familial neonatal-infantile seizures (OMIM #607745), with underlying mechanisms that range from gain- to loss-of-function on protein level.¹⁵ In such cases, therapeutic strategies and feasibility assessments must be tailored to the specific disease entity rather than generalized to the gene as a whole. This distinction highlights the importance of the “lumping versus splitting” framework—whether to consider multiple clinical entities under a unified diagnosis or treat them as discrete disorders based on pathomechanism and clinical course.¹⁶ To identify the specific disease entity, it is necessary to understand which variant gives rise to which clinical phenotype (genotype-phenotype correlation), and thus, an evaluation is ultimately made at variant level.

A simplified 3-step process to determine the variant-disease association could look as follows: 1) establish pathogenicity of the variant; 2) determine predicted or experimentally validated functional effect of the variant and its plausibility of the relationship with the phenotype of the case

examined; and 3) the classification into a sub-phenotype (where present in a disease group) based on the literature of data from large gene-specific registries.

To generally establish a gene-disease relationship, frameworks and guidelines are available that can support the process, also taking into account the scarcity of information available for rare diseases.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ For example, the Clinical Genome Resource Gene Curation Working Group has established a Gene-Disease Validity Curation Process.²⁰ Santen *et al.* provide a framework for evaluating the level of evidence for a gene–disease relationship,²¹ incorporating criteria including variant type, disease model availability, clinical presentation, and variant population frequency. Yates *et al.* recently presented a structured curation process for Gene2Phenotype (G2P).²² This process combines clinical, bioinformatic, and functional evidence to attribute a confidence level to a given gene-disease relationship. For establishing new gene-disease associations, in order to establish therapeutic eligibility, we recommend working with disease experts who can support these curations.

1.1.3 Penetrance and expressivity

When assessing the gene-disease association, two further genetic concepts become relevant: penetrance and expressivity. Penetrance refers to the proportion of individuals carrying a pathogenic variant who develop the associated phenotype. Expressivity describes the extent to which a phenotype manifests in an individual with a pathogenic variant.

If penetrance is reduced or incomplete, the specific variant does not always lead to a phenotype. Penetrance can be as low as a few percent.²³ The degree of penetrance is important in deciding if and when to start (developing) therapeutic intervention for both individualized and generalized therapies. In the case of low penetrance, a molecular diagnosis alone may not justify therapeutic development for individualized cases as it cannot be guaranteed that the individual will develop the disease. The degree of penetrance further challenges generalized therapeutic development as it reduces the number of individuals who will benefit from treatment. Penetrance also affects the justification of pre-symptomatic treatment, especially when not all individuals carrying a variant develop a disease phenotype.

Variable expressivity describes the phenomenon by which individuals carrying the same pathogenic variant exhibit different clinical presentations.²³ In case of complete penetrance, every individual carrying the variant will develop the disease, albeit with different severity/clinical presentations. Variable expressivity should especially be taken into account when considering generalized therapeutic developments. Similarly, genetic therapy available for variants that exhibit variable expressivity will have variable effects in different individuals, especially when affected tissues are diverse and cannot (yet) be targeted with the same therapeutic strategy.

Reduced penetrance and variable expressivity can occur simultaneously, further complicating therapeutic decision making.

1.1.4 Mode of Pathogenicity

Having a clear understanding of gene- and variant-specific disease mechanisms is important for assessing eligibility for genetic therapies, especially those that do not aim at directly correcting the pathogenic variant (editing). Once the genotype-phenotype association is confirmed for a monogenic disorder, one should consider utilizing publicly available databases and published literature for evidence of the disease mechanism, checking at a variant level. Pathogenic variants can be causative for a genetic disorder through three major protein-consequence mechanisms: loss-of-function (LoF), gain-of-function (GoF), and dominant-negative (DN) effects.²⁴

Loss of function (LoF)

LoF variants, including partial (hypomorphic) and complete (null), reduce wildtype protein production or activity. The variant can either be a copy number loss variant, a truncating variant, splicing variant, a missense/indel variant, or a regulatory variant. Copy number variants (CNVs) can result in a loss of an entire gene from the genome. LoF due to an early truncation of a coding sequence resulting from nonsense, frameshift, or splicing variants introducing a premature stop codon can lead to nonsense-mediated mRNA decay (NMD) or the production of a nonfunctional protein. Missense and indel variants may cause LoF if they disrupt regulatory or functional domains, leading to impaired transcription, translation, or the production of a nonfunctional or unstable protein.

In the case of monoallelic LoF, one wildtype allele is still present and fully functional. The outcome of such a situation is dependent on the dosage sensitivity of the gene. When a monoallelic LoF variant is disease-causing, this is referred to as haploinsufficiency.²⁵ Disease-causing monoallelic LoF variants can either be inherited or arise through *de novo* occurrences. Incomplete penetrance and variable expressivity in monoallelic LoF genes are more challenging to define as the genotype-phenotype correlation may not be apparent. However, such occurrences are common in monoallelic LoF genes, and thus important to consider. For therapeutic purposes, the general goal is to increase or replace protein production and/or function as close to wildtype levels as possible. The realistic amount of protein function required for therapeutic benefits is dependent on the specific dosage sensitivity of a gene.

In biallelic LoF cases, both alleles carry a LoF variant, resulting in no functional copies of the gene. In this case, either both alleles have the same LoF variant (homozygous), or the two alleles have two different LoF variants (compound heterozygous). Similarly, there is no functional copy of a gene if there is a LoF variant in an X-linked or Y-linked gene in males (hemizygous), presenting similar to bi-allelic LoF cases. Bi-allelic LoF diseases are recessively inherited, meaning that heterozygous carriers exist in the population and are unaffected or mildly affected. The amenability of bi-allelic LoF disorders for genetic intervention is dependent on the specific type of variant, but the general goal is to restore some level of protein production and/or protein function. If a gene is susceptible to only bi-allelic LoF, the gene is considered haplosufficient, therefore restoring dosage to carrier protein levels at approximately 50% wildtype level, is sufficient for therapeutic purposes. Notably, restoring the affected protein in cases of complete loss-of-function (null variants, e.g. biallelic gene

deletions) where no truncated or inactive version of the protein had previously been expressed might induce immune responses against the newly expressed wildtype protein.²⁶

Gain of function (GoF)

GoF (hypermorphic) variants can either increase wildtype protein activity through constitutive activation, loss of inhibitory regulation, or increase wildtype protein production or stability, leading to overexpression. On the genetic level, the variant can be a copy number gain, a nonsense or frameshift variant, a splicing variant, a missense/indel variant, or a regulatory variant. Copy number variants can add an entire gene into the genome and result in overproduction of transcripts and the respective protein.²⁷ Nonsense or frameshift variants that remove an autoinhibitory domain can lead to a constitutively active protein.²⁸ Similarly, splicing variants that remove autoinhibitory domains or add an extra functional domain can lead to a hyperactive protein.²⁹ Missense and indel variants can cause GoF consequences through a variety of mechanisms, for example, by stabilizing the active conformation of the protein, by disrupting autoinhibitory contacts, or by enhancing substrate or ligand affinity.^{30,31}

GoF genes are typically monoallelic, where a single allele with the GoF variant is disease-causing. Variants can be inherited or occur *de novo*. For therapeutic purposes, the general goal is to reduce protein amount or lower protein activity. For genes also intolerant to LoF variants, careful dosing and/or an allele-selective approach is required to ensure that beneficial effects can be achieved (see section 1.2.1 Knockdown, Allele Specificity).

Similar to the hypermorphic GoF variants, some variants, known as neomorphic variants, can cause the gain of a new function that is toxic to the cell. For example, nonsense or frameshift variants that do not cause NMD can introduce a novel C-terminal tail that can confer new interactions or incorrect localization.³² Splicing variants can include cryptic exons that add new protein function/localization. Missense and indel variants can create novel interaction surfaces to attain new binding partners or alter the original functional domains.³³ The general therapeutic goal for neomorphic variants is to remove the novel functions gained and, if possible, restore wildtype function. For genes also intolerant to monoallelic LoF, careful dosing and/or an allele-specific approach can be required as discussed below.

Dominant-negative (DN)

DN (antimorphic) variants are monoallelic variants that interfere with the function of the wildtype protein.³⁴ The variant is often a missense/indel variant but can be a truncating variant that escapes NMD or a splicing variant.^{35,36} Variants are dominantly inherited or occur *de novo*. For therapeutic purposes, the goal is to remove the toxic protein while preserving or increasing wildtype protein levels. Although not preferred, it can also be considered to solely increase the wildtype protein levels to shift the ratio of wildtype to mutant protein towards more wildtype protein.³⁷ This approach has recently been applied in a gene replacement therapy for *IRF2BPL*.³⁸

Another approach to tackling DN variants uses a combination of knockdown via ASOs, siRNA or RNAi and simultaneous replacement of the gene product via gene replacement. This approach

has been referred to in the literature as “suppress and replace”, “silence and repair” or “silence and replace”.³⁹ This therapeutic strategy has also been considered for toxic GoF variants and there is a current trial ongoing for Oculopharyngeal Muscular Dystrophy With Dysphagia (ClinicalTrials.gov ID NCT06185673).^{40,41}

Mixed gain- and loss-of-function

Not all variants show an effect that can clearly be categorized as GoF, LoF, or DN. Some variants show a mix of effects where part of the function was lost, and another function was gained. These are sometimes referred to as mixed gain- and loss-of-function or mixed loss- and gain-of-function variants.⁴² It should also be noted that proteins can have different functions in different pathways, sometimes even tissue-dependent, and it should be delineated which functions are affected in which pathway and tissue, depending on a given variant.

For therapeutic evaluation, it is relevant to understand the clinical consequences of this mix of effects. Should only the LoF be relevant for the clinical phenotype or only the GoF effect, then this is the effect that will be evaluated for therapeutic eligibility and potentially corrected. If both are relevant, it should be understood which one is the effect that is leading to more severe clinical symptoms, and, where possible, correct based on this knowledge. Of course, editing approaches correcting the variant back to the wildtype will correct any of these effects.

One example of a mixed gain- and loss-of-function variant being treated with a knockdown approach is the NM_021007.3(SCN2A):c.2558G>A p.(p.Arg853Gln) variant in *SCN2A*.⁴³ A knockdown ASO therapy has been developed for an individual carrying this variant which has already been delivered clinically.⁴⁴

Overall, understanding the pathomechanism of a given variant determines which genetic interventions are appropriate and viable.

Pathomechanism assessment

To delineate the pathomechanism for a given disease, or ideally the variant, we recommend a thorough literature study. Sufficient functional evidence should be available to determine the pathomechanism with high quality experimental design, including the presence of relevant controls and necessary repetitions. Unfortunately, for the vast majority of genomic variants, we do not yet fully understand the pathomechanism. Often, after the first few variants for a novel gene-disease association are assessed and published, there is a loss of incentive to continue functional modelling. Moreover, the impact on one model system may not accurately reflect what happens in the individual carrying the variant. Due to the importance of the pathomechanism in selecting a suitable therapeutic approach, it is important to continue to pursue rigorous functional studies.

We generally do not recommend using prediction models to determine the pathogenicity of a variant, but rather to rely on functional data. In some instances, one can deduce the pathomechanism of a variant from the phenotype of the patient, e.g. onset and severity of seizures in channelopathies, the response to different drugs or overall clinical presentation.^{45,46}

Notably, there are resources available with curated information on the pathomechanisms of genes and diseases that can aid in the assessments. For example, the Clinical Genome Resource

(ClinGen) provides expert-curated information on the clinical relevance of genes and genetic variants (<https://search.clinicalgenome.org/kb/genes/curations>), including the gene-disease validity, dosage sensitivity, clinical actionability, variant pathogenicity and pharmacogenomics.¹⁰ ClinGen evaluates and classifies gene–disease relationships based on strength of evidence (e.g. definitive, strong, limited), and determines whether genes are sensitive to dosage changes, such as haploinsufficiency or triplosensitivity. It also offers data on clinical actionability for genes with known medical interventions and the efficacy and nature of such interventions. Under the Gene-Disease Validity curations, there are two tabs for Genetic Evidence and Experimental Evidence. Genetic Evidence supplies case-specific information curated from published case studies, and the respective functional study performed in each publication. Experimental Evidence curates *in vitro* and model organism functional experiments that define the molecular disease mechanisms of the gene.

1.1.5 Dosage sensitivity

A final molecular consideration when assessing a gene or disease for therapeutic intervention is dosage sensitivity. This describes how tolerant a gene is to changes in its expression level, and how deviations, either reductions (e.g. haploinsufficiency, loss-of-function intolerance) or increases (e.g. triplosensitivity), contribute to disease.⁴⁷

To be more precise, one should look at the range of dosage needed to maintain physiological function. Defining the lower and upper bounds of this range provides a practical framework for therapeutic design. It indicates (i) the degree of upregulation or downregulation required to achieve phenotypic rescue, and (ii) the limits that should not be exceeded by genetic intervention to avoid toxicity or secondary pathology.

This concept is particularly important given that therapeutic effects are rarely uniform across cells and tissues. The different genetic technologies will typically lead to variable expression levels across different tissues. Overall, genes with a narrow tolerated dosage range present a greater challenge, as even modest over or under correction may fall outside the therapeutic window.

Furthermore, dosage sensitivity must be interpreted in a tissue-specific context. These considerations are most relevant for the target tissue, and any additional tissues reached by the therapy. For example, LoF intolerance in a non-target tissue may be less concerning if the therapeutic modality does not reach that tissue. Conversely, off-target exposure in sensitive tissues may impose constraints on dosing or modality selection. Dosage sensitivity should therefore always be evaluated alongside tissue targeting and biodistribution.

Haploinsufficiency

Haploinsufficiency occurs when a single functional allele does not produce enough protein to maintain normal physiological function.⁴⁷ This is typically associated with autosomal dominant disorders caused by LoF variants.

To assess whether a gene is associated with haploinsufficiency, several publicly available resources can be used. A simple search through the web or literature databases can provide some insight. Reviewing GeneReviews (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1116/>), if available, can also prove useful. Quantitative indicators of haploinsufficiency can be obtained, such as the

probability of loss-of-function intolerance (pLI) and loss-of-function observed/expected upper bound fraction (LOEUF) scores from gnomAD (<https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/>),^{48,49} as well as the haploinsufficiency score (HI) curated by the ClinGen consortium (<https://search.clinicalgenome.org/kb/gene-dosage>) or DECIPHER (<https://www.deciphergenomics.org/>). Furthermore, the probability of haploinsufficiency (pHaplo) score can be used to determine the probability of haploinsufficiency.⁵⁰

Note that each quantitative indicator defines haploinsufficiency differently. Typically, the thresholds outlined in **Suppl. Table 1** can be used as a guide for interpretation. It is also possible to assess a potential haploinsufficiency by checking how many carriers of LoF variants have been reported in public databases/datasets like gnomAD or the UK Biobank and, where available, how they present clinically. However, such measures cannot provide a definitive answer. We generally recommend using expert-curated scoring systems instead of prediction tools and computationally generated scores.

Triplosensitivity

Triplosensitivity occurs when an extra copy or increased expression of a gene leads to a disease. One resource to consider for determining triplosensitivity is the ClinGen Triplosensitivity Score (TS). The probability of triplosensitivity (pTriplo) score can also be utilized.^{49,50} This score is, for example, available through the UCSC Genome Browser.

Suppl. Table 1: Interpretation of quantitative indicators of haploinsufficiency and triplosensitivity. GnomAD scores provided refer to gnomAD v4.0.

Tool	Interpretation
pLI Score	Values ≥ 0.9 indicate that a gene appears to be intolerant of loss-of-function variation. ⁵¹
LOEUF Score	Values < 0.6 indicate that a gene appears to be intolerant of loss-of-function variation. ⁵¹
DECIPHER %HI	Values $< 10\%$ predict that a gene is more likely to exhibit haploinsufficiency. ⁵¹
ClinGen HI Score	ClinGen haploinsufficiency score of 3 (sufficient evidence) indicates haploinsufficiency being a cause of disease. ⁵²
pHaplo Score	Scores ≥ 0.86 indicate that the average effect sizes of deletions are as strong as the loss-of-function of genes known to be constrained against protein truncating variants. ⁵³
ClinGen TS Score	ClinGen triplosensitivity score of 3 (sufficient evidence) indicates triplosensitivity being a cause of disease. ⁵²
pTriplo	Scores ≥ 0.94 indicate that the average effect sizes of deletions are as strong as the loss-of-function of genes known to be constrained against protein truncating variants. ⁵³

As mentioned before, it will not always be necessary to determine all of this information. Especially for editing approaches where correction back to the wildtype variant is possible, the pathomechanism of the variant will not be of relevance.

While the same could be said about dosage sensitivity considerations, we would like to stress that this will depend on editing efficacies. Correction of LoF variants will need to achieve a high enough editing efficacy to push the gene product over the minimum threshold needed to sustain physiological function; and for GoF and DN negative variants, the editing efficacy should be high enough in the target tissue to sufficiently reduce the levels of the toxic gene product.

1.2 Therapeutic approaches: knockdown vs. upregulation

Once a gene-disease association has been established and the pathomechanism and dosage sensitivity are defined, one can consider the most suitable therapeutic approach. Gene- and RNA-editing approaches are typically independent of the pathomechanism and dosage sensitivity (with restrictions mentioned above), if the goal is to correct the pathogenic variants themselves. This also applies to ASO strategies that can correct aberrant splicing and lead to the generation of the wildtype transcript. Most other therapeutic interventions are based on the pathomechanism and dosage sensitivity and can broadly be categorized as knockdown and upregulation approaches. Though detailed molecular considerations are beyond the scope of these recommendations, understanding the basics and applicability of a knockdown versus an upregulation strategy is crucial for understanding the eligibility of a gene or disease towards different therapeutic interventions.

1.2.1 Knockdown

Knockdown refers to the reduction of gene expression and can be achieved using, for example, gapmer ASOs, siRNAs, AAV-delivered microRNAs or CRISPR editing. These approaches lead to decreased RNA levels and reduced protein expression, and are particularly useful when the underlying disease mechanism involves toxic GoF or DN.⁵⁴ Examples of knockdown genetic medicines include tofersen (Qalsody) for the treatment of *SOD1*-associated amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS, OMIM #105400),⁵⁵ and inotersen (Tegsedi) for the treatment of hereditary transthyretin-mediated amyloidosis (OMIM #105210).⁵⁶ An example of an N=1 knockdown genetic medicine includes an allele-specific ASO targeting a single nucleotide polymorphism in the *KIF1A* gene, in phase with a dominant negative missense variant.⁵⁷ Additionally, adeno-associated virus (AAV) based therapy to deliver microRNAs to lower protein production for hypermorphs has been explored, for example, for *SOD1*-associated ALS.⁵⁸

Other than for direct correction of a pathogenic variant, CRISPR-based approaches can also be applied for general knockdown therapies. For example, a currently running human clinical trial is using a base editor to create a frameshift variant for inactivation of *PCSK9* in the liver to reduce disease-driving low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in patients with Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) (ClinicalTrials.gov NCT06458010).^{59,60}

Allele Specificity

In diseases where a complete loss of function is tolerated, targeting both alleles for knockdown may be acceptable. For variants causing a DN effect or for genes that are sensitive to low dosages, allele-specific approaches (ASOs, siRNA, allele-specific CRISPR nucleases), designed to target only the mutant allele, either via a single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) or the pathogenic variant itself, should be considered.⁵⁴ While this approach can significantly constrain therapeutic design (e.g. ASO or siRNA sequence), it helps preserve the wildtype allele, thereby theoretically maintaining 50% of normal protein expression. Especially in cases of DN variants, selectively targeting the mutant allele is critical to preserve as much wild-type function as possible.

Whether a GoF variant/disease requires an allele-selective or general knockdown will highly be dependent on the disease, the dosage sensitivity of the gene in the target tissue and any phenotypes associated with LoF variants (see below). These considerations should be made in consultation with relevant disease and gene/protein experts. However, it might be worth mentioning that also among the experts, opinions on allele-selective vs. non-allele-selective strategies differ and we will need additional data to make such decisions more confidentially in the future.

An example of where a shift from a general knockdown to an allele-selective approach is currently being discussed is Huntington's diseases;⁶¹ after a general knockdown approach in a clinical trial did not meet clinical endpoints and patients performed worse compared to the placebo group.⁶²

Haploinsufficiency

Special considerations are needed for genes associated with haploinsufficiency. In such cases, therapeutic knockdown could lead to reduced gene dosage, leading to phenotypes associated with insufficient gene expression. Examples are *SCN2A* and *SCN8A*, which are implicated in both LoF and GoF mechanisms.^{63,64} Therefore, when haploinsufficiency is also a known disease mechanism in the target tissue, it is important to evaluate whether the phenotype associated with reduced dosage are milder than those caused by GoF or DN variants and whether this justifies the (allele-selective) knockdown of the transcripts.

Considerations for X-linked and Y-linked disorders

Additional considerations apply in X- and Y-linked disorders. In males, knockdown of an X- or Y-linked gene may result in complete loss of gene function; therefore, it must first be established that such a complete loss is compatible with health. The *CLCN4*-related condition is one example where such considerations are ongoing.⁶⁵ In females with X-linked disorders, the effects of X-inactivation on gene dosage must also be carefully evaluated to determine whether a knockdown approach is safe.

1.2.2 Upregulation

Upregulation refers to increasing genetic expression. This can, for example, be achieved using ASOs to upregulate the wildtype allele,⁶⁶ gene replacement, or mRNA replacement therapy. These approaches are particularly suited for disorders caused by monoallelic LoF variants (haploinsufficiency) or biallelic LoF variants. Attention should be paid to the fact that upregulation

from the wildtype allele only works for haploinsufficiency disorders where the wildtype allele is still intact. Examples of upregulation genetic medicines include nusinersen (Spinraza), a splice-switching ASO that promotes *SMN2* exon 7 inclusion in spinal muscular atrophy, and Zolgensma, an AAV-based *SMN1* gene replacement therapy also targeting SMN deficiency.^{67,68}

It is essential to consider dosage sensitivity and the risk of triplosensitivity when evaluating upregulation as a therapeutic strategy. While upregulation therapies aim to restore protein levels, excessive expression can be harmful in genes with tightly regulated dosage thresholds.

In some cases, upregulation is also an option for DN variants. Apart from the *IRF2BPL* example discussed before, two additional examples are *GABRG2* and *HTT*. In a truncating *GABRG2* variant that disrupted incorporation of the wildtype subunit into GABA_A receptors, upregulating wildtype levels with a gene replacement therapy was able to outcompete the DN effect and rescue the electrophysiological phenotype.⁶⁹ In Huntington’s disease embryonic stem cell lines carrying mutant HTT, the expression of a full-length wildtype HTT was able to partially rescue the disease phenotype.⁷⁰

While these examples provide evidence of this approach being a suitable therapeutic strategy, upregulation of the wildtype in diseases associated with a DN effect should be considered with utmost care. As discussed in 1.1.4, a “suppress and replace” approach will also lead to an upregulation while simultaneously abolishing the mutant allele.

1.2.3 Other strategies

It is important to note that the choice of therapeutic strategy does not always fall neatly into the dichotomy of upregulation versus downregulation. As already mentioned above, editing approaches on DNA and RNA level can be used to correct the pathogenic variant back to the wildtype genotype. Similarly, splice-modulating ASOs can correct aberrant splicing and lead to the generation of the wildtype transcript.

Notably, splicing-modulating ASOs can also be used to skip exons harboring pathogenic variants, potentially restoring the reading frame and producing a truncated but (partially) functional protein product.⁵⁴ This is exemplified by the exon skipping ASO therapies developed for Duchenne muscular dystrophy (OMIM #310200).⁷¹ These strategies are applicable regardless of whether the underlying mechanism involves a GoF, LoF or DN effects, as these approaches are not modulating dosage.

In summary, the development of genetic therapies requires a detailed understanding of the underlying disease mechanism, including whether it involves LoF, GoF, or DN effects. While upregulation and knockdown strategies offer powerful tools to restore physiological balance, their implementation must also consider gene dosage sensitivity, including the risks of haploinsufficiency and triplosensitivity. Suppl. Table 2 provides a summary of the two strategies.

Suppl. Table 2: Overview of knockdown versus upregulation strategies

Strategy	Knockdown	Upregulation
----------	-----------	--------------

Pathomechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gain-of-function ○ Dominant negative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Loss-of-function (mono- and biallelic) ○ Dominant negative (in specific cases)
Therapeutic compounds/drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gapmer ASO ○ Small interfering RNA (siRNA) ○ CRISPR nucleases ○ Editing to generate truncating variants (DNA and RNA level) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ mRNA replacement ○ Gene replacement ○ ASO upregulation from the WT allele (in case of haploinsufficiency)
Examples (general)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Inotersen (ASO) ○ Tofersen (ASO) ○ Vutrisiran (siRNA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nusinersen (ASO) ○ Zolgensma (AAV gene replacement) ○ Zorevunersen (ASO)
Examples (N=1/few)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>KIF1A</i> knockdown (ASO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>AP4M1</i> gene replacement (AAV gene replacement)

2. Clinical considerations

Before starting any genetic therapy development, one should consider the overall clinical presentation of the disorder, the phenotypic spectrum, the typical stage of disease at diagnosis, and disease progression. In addition, it is highly relevant to determine whether there currently is the possibility to efficiently deliver a suitable therapy to the target tissue.

The following section provides information on general clinical considerations that will be applicable long-term, and also covers considerations on specific therapeutic modalities, including a discussion on what is possible now and what might become possible in the future. Given the rapid development of genetic interventions in recent years, many of the current limitations are likely to be overcome in the near future.

2.1 Natural history data

Natural history describes how a condition develops and progresses over time under standard care.⁷² Collecting natural history data prior to initiating genetic treatment is important to enable a robust assessment of therapeutic benefits. In some cases, such data may also be generated in parallel with therapeutic development.

A key caveat in this process is that determining what constitutes “sufficient” natural history data or a “reasonably clear” understanding of disease progression is inherently context-dependent. Expectations vary by disease characteristics, geography, and regulatory authority. For example, in severe, rapidly progressive pediatric-onset disorders, with a clearly defined and well-understood pathomechanism, a limited number of well-documented cases may be sufficient to support

therapeutic development, particularly when no alternative treatments exist. In contrast, more heterogeneous or slowly progressive conditions typically require systematic, longitudinal data across diverse populations to adequately define disease trajectories.

High-quality natural history data collected using standardized measures are essential for informing clinical trial endpoint development and enabling comparisons across studies.⁷² The gold standard is a multicenter, prospective natural history study. When prospective data collection is not feasible, retrospective studies, such as those based on disease- or gene-specific registries, may be used. However, their utility depends on the completeness and quality of previously collected data. Since natural history data are often used as historical controls in rare disease therapy development, rigorous study design and execution are particularly critical.

Unfortunately, for many rare genetic disorders, no natural history data or registries are available, and, at most, a few case studies can be found in the literature. In such cases, to obtain a basic understanding of a disease, databases like OMIM (<https://www.omim.org/>), Gene Reviews (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1116/>), and Orphanet (<https://www.orpha.net>) are valuable resources.¹¹⁻¹³ In addition, websites like GTE_x (<https://gtexportal.org/home/>) and Protein Atlas (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/>) provide information on the expression of the affected gene and localization of the protein,^{73,74} helping to determine potential affected tissues and signaling pathways. Many rare diseases have dedicated pages established by patient advocacy groups (<https://www.orpha.net/en/patient-organisations>, <https://www.rareportal.org.au/>, <https://rarediseases.info.nih.gov/>) that are useful for gathering information on symptoms and clinical presentations and may even list symptoms that have been left out of case reports.¹²

Notably, for individualized therapeutic developments, the patient itself may serve as a resource for natural history data and serve as its own control. In such cases, where possible, the patient and their caregivers may be consulted to obtain natural history data, including careful studying of the patient's files. For these individual developments, it is important to specify which symptoms are potentially treatable and why a therapeutic development is potentially beneficial.

As part of collecting natural history data, it is important to clearly define disease sub-phenotypes. This enables a more precise understanding of the natural history within specific sub-populations. Such stratification can inform whether a given subgroup is amenable to treatment, as well as guide the selection of clinical outcome measures and the identification of the therapeutic window.

2.2 Target tissues

To understand whether a disease can be treated with the currently available technologies, one has to assess which tissues and cell types need to be targeted and if there are suitable delivery methods available (see also section 2.3).⁷⁵

This includes distinguishing between primary and secondary affected tissues, as the most appropriate therapeutic target may not be the tissue where symptoms manifest, but rather where the underlying defect arises. For example, phenylketonuria is a metabolic disorder caused by the deficiency of phenylalanine hydroxylase, a liver enzyme required to metabolize phenylalanine. As a result, this amino acid accumulates in the blood and the brain, leading to severe brain damage.⁷⁶ In

this case, one would have to target and treat the liver to ensure proper brain function in individuals affected by phenylketonuria.

In addition to identifying the correct tissue, it is critical to consider whether the relevant cell types within that tissue can be effectively reached. Even when the tissue of origin is accessible, therapeutic success may be limited if the delivery system does not efficiently target the specific cells driving disease pathology.

To identify the target tissue and cell type, it is recommended to dive into the literature and understand what has been published on a given disease and the clinical presentation. For the very rare genetic disorders, the origin of the disease in terms of cell type might not always be known, and additional functional studies might be necessary before a therapy can be developed. Generally, understanding the expression pattern of a gene over time, e.g. prenatally and postnatally throughout the years, can help identify tissues to be targeted. Tissue expression can, for example, be found through the GTEx Portal (<https://www.gtexportal.org/home/>) or the Human Protein Atlas (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/>).^{73,74}

In some instances, targeting a different gene within an affected signaling pathway might be more suitable than targeting the gene of origin. Such considerations should be made with caution and only if the mechanism of disease in the secondary tissue is well understood. An example for targeting a different gene is the application of inclisiran (Leqvio) for the treatment of heterozygous familial hypercholesterolemia. While familial hypercholesterolemia can be caused by variants in *APOB*, *LDLR*, and *PCSK9*, inclisiran specifically targets the mRNA transcript of *PCSK9*, reducing the amount of PCSK9 protein. This increases the availability of LDL-cholesterol receptors in the liver, which, in turn, enhances the clearance of LDL-cholesterol from the bloodstream.⁷⁷

For some disorders, one might also consider delivery to multiple tissues using the same therapeutic modality. For example, in neurological disorders that affect the retina and brain, a combined intravitreal and intrathecal injection using ASOs might be possible. As different affected tissues may require delivery with additional systems or different therapeutic modalities, the determination becomes increasingly complex. These discussions require a thorough risk-benefit assessment.

When multiple tissues are affected, two key considerations emerge: Is there one organ/tissue/cell type that is mainly affected and responsible for the clinical presentation, and can this be targeted? Then, one might consider only targeting one tissue to improve the patient's quality of life. If the most affected tissue cannot be targeted, the question arises whether there is another organ system that could be targeted and would this lead to an alleviation of symptoms and improvement in the quality of life? Then, one can consider such a therapeutic option, again weighing the risks and benefits of such an approach.

The decision on the treatability of target tissue should always be made with the current possibilities and limitations of the delivery systems in mind. With improvements in delivery, more tissues will become targetable.

2.3 Delivery feasibility

Efficient delivery to the target tissue remains a central challenge in genetic therapy development and a key determinant of whether a disease is amenable to treatment.⁷⁸ Despite ongoing advances in delivery strategies, limitations persist, and feasibility ultimately depends on the specific combination of delivery system and therapeutic modality (Suppl. Figure 1).

Gene editing and gene replacement therapies can be delivered *ex vivo* as well as *in vivo*. Delivery can be achieved via different systems, including viral vectors and lipid nanoparticles. Currently, *ex vivo* editing is possible for different cell types of the immune system, such as T-cells. *In vivo* gene editing using lipid nanoparticles is currently possible for the liver, while approaches targeting retinal, brain, and muscle cells are under development assessed. For viral delivery systems, often an adeno-associated virus (AAV) is used. AAVs can target different tissues, even specific cell types, depending on the virus serotype.⁷⁹ *In vivo* gene replacement therapies have so far mainly been developed for the brain (e.g. Zolgensma), eye (retina) (e.g. Luxturna), and liver (e.g. Hemgenix and Roctavian). Notably, with AAV gene replacement, the replaced gene stays episomal, which is relevant to consider when targeting regenerating tissues, for example the liver, where the transgene expression decreases with each cell division. Additional review of specific delivery systems is outside of the scope of this guidance; we recommend further literature.^{80,81}

Tissue-targeted delivery for RNA therapeutics, specifically ASOs and siRNAs via local injection, is currently possible to the brain, spinal cord, and retina. Additionally, systemic delivery to the liver as trimeric N-acetyl galactosamine (GalNac) conjugates is also feasible.⁸² RNA editing is currently being tested for alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency using a GalNac-conjugated A-to-I RNA editing oligonucleotide (ClinicalTrials.gov NCT06405633).⁸³ Collectively, these delivery capabilities position central nervous system and liver indications among the most near-term and technically tractable targets for RNA therapeutic development.⁷⁸ Notably, although different exon skipping therapies have been developed and approved for Duchenne muscular dystrophy, delivery to the muscle remains insufficient. Therefore, systemic muscle disorders remain less favorable near-term targets for RNA therapeutics, primarily due to current delivery limitations. Delivery to the muscle using new conjugates is an area of ongoing research,^{84,85} and better delivery systems should become available in the future. Similarly, delivery to the kidneys has seen recent advances.⁸⁶ Other RNA interventions, such as mRNA replacement therapies, have been clinically delivered to individuals with monogenic diseases as part of clinical trials, but have not yet received market authorization.⁸⁷ mRNA replacement therapies can be delivered with lipid nanoparticles and can, for example, target the liver.⁸⁷

When considering the delivery system, one should also determine what off-target effects are expected for the delivery. For example, dosage sensitivity of a gene product can be tissue dependent, and while a down- or upregulation of a gene in the target tissue will not only be tolerated but serve as a disease-modifying therapy, this tolerance might not exist for other tissues that will also be targeted by the chosen delivery system.^{88,89} Delivery to this off-target tissue could lead to adverse reactions. Conversely, dosage sensitivity in a tissue that will not be targeted by the chosen delivery route and method should not limit therapeutic development.

To understand these potential off-target effects, one should look into the drug's pharmacokinetics. Pharmacokinetics describes the interaction of the administered drug with the

body throughout the entire exposure cycle from absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME).⁹⁰

Suppl. Figure 1. Overview of tissues for which market-approved gene replacement, gene editing and oligonucleotide therapies have been delivered. Created in BioRender. Van Esbroeck, A. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/3s8x2ke>

2.4 Types of symptoms and clinical outcome measures

Apart from understanding the affected and target tissues, the clinical presentation, meaning the symptoms that manifest in affected individuals, is crucial to evaluate. Most importantly, evaluating whether a disease is amenable to treatment requires considering whether meaningful therapeutic effects can be achieved and measured—such as reversing symptoms, slowing or halting disease progression, or improving functional outcomes. Measurable symptoms could include seizures, psychosis, temper tantrums, migraines, falls, walking distance, etc., where either duration, frequency, severity or type can be determined. Diseases with measurable manifestations, ideally ones that can also be measured at home by patients and caretakers, are strong therapeutic candidates as treatment efficacy can be evaluated. This also includes the use of wearables and, where possible, doctor visits via telehealth, which will especially enable patients and families without direct or close access to hospitals to receive genetic therapies.

Reversible symptoms should be distinguished from irreversible manifestations, such as organ aplasia, for which disease-modifying interventions are not currently feasible. It is also

important to assess whether seemingly treatable symptoms, such as seizures, result from structural abnormalities and are therefore unlikely to respond to genetic therapy. Disease severity is also an important consideration. Diseases with milder phenotypes should be considered with caution, and the benefit-risk ratio should always be taken into account before developing an experimental therapy. Notably, the FDA guidance for individualized ASOs is for 'severely debilitating or life-threatening genetic disease'.⁹¹ Considerations of what severity level is suitable for a therapy development might change over time, including the considerations for benefit-risk ratios as we better understand the safety and efficacy profiles of the different therapeutic modalities. At this point, diseases with milder phenotypes may also become eligible targets for genetic therapies.

Special considerations should be taken for (neuro-)developmental disorders. While some developmental disorders show a progressive aspect (e.g. Neurodevelopmental disorder with progressive spasticity and brain white matter abnormalities (NEDSWMA, OMIM#619026)),⁹² many are characterized by a delay in developmental milestones. For a long time, these disorders were considered suboptimal targets. However, there is now evidence of multiple different diseases across multiple patients indicating neurodevelopmental disorders can be treated, providing opportunity for patients to gain new milestones later in life. Examples include *KIF1A*-associated neurodevelopmental disorder and Angelman syndrome.^{57,93}

Overall, the types of symptoms define possible clinical outcome measures. Only when clear outcome measures can be translated into a clinical benefit, should a genetic intervention be deemed suitable. What constitutes suitable clinical outcome measures will differ from disease to disease, and the regulatory body in question, and must be agreed upon with the treating clinical team and ideally the patient community. When considering individualized genetic therapy development, clinical outcome measures will have to be defined for each patient and might differ from patient to patient, even when carrying the same pathogenic variant.⁹⁴

The use of biomarkers as clinical outcome measures, especially for individualized genetic therapies, is currently debated in the field. Biomarkers can include biochemical markers (like blood, urine, saliva, cerebrospinal fluid measurements), but also measures of brain activity using an EEG, for example. While biomarkers can help elucidate reactions of the body following genetic therapy, these should not be used as sole outcome measures. The ultimate goal is always to achieve clinical benefit, and appropriate measurements should be made to assess clinical benefit.

2.5 Therapeutic window of opportunity

Once measurable symptoms and clinical outcome measures are defined, one has to consider when a treatment initiation is most beneficial, and how the time it takes to develop a therapy will influence the treatability of an individual.

For every disease, the optimal time point of intervention and timeframe during which an intervention can still lead to a clinical benefit is considered the therapeutic window of opportunity. This window is dependent on the progression rate of the disease, the different disease stages and factors like the developmental window and the regenerative capability of the target tissues. For each disease, this window will look different and can contain a timeframe of months to years.

2.5.1 Disease progression

Relevant to consider in this context are progressive diseases. A therapeutic intervention holds the promise to slow down or halt disease progression altogether. This defines clear clinical benefits and also serves as a suitable clinical outcome measure, particularly when disease-specific progression or severity scores are available to support a standardized disease trajectory evaluation. Examples include progressive vision loss, loss of ambulation, regression of motor skills, and cognitive decline.

However, progressive diseases do not come without their challenges and the rate of progression needs to be considered carefully. For slowly progressive diseases (e.g., Charcot-Marie Tooth, *CMT1A* and *CMTX1*) where progression is measured over many years,⁹⁵ a therapeutic effect might be challenging to define, and thus, therapeutic success will be difficult to assess. In such cases, it should be evaluated if the risk of an experimental treatment justifies a potentially slower disease progression. Improved understanding of the safety profiles of genetic interventions will affect the risk calculus over time. We recommend contacting experts on a given disease to understand progression rates. Patient/family-reported progression of symptoms can also be very useful to collect and define disease progression. Especially with diseases only described in a few patients and potential genotype-phenotype differences in disease progression, these decisions and considerations will have to be made carefully until a better understanding of the disease in question is available.

Conversely, diseases that are rapidly progressive (e.g., amyotrophic lateral sclerosis) might become too severe within the timeframe required for therapy development, and by the time the treatment is ready, the potential benefit may be lost. This, of course, is mainly a consideration for diseases where the therapy would have to be developed from scratch and remains a key challenge when developing a therapy for a single individual or a very small group of patients. In the case of fast progressive disorders where multiple patients are affected and more patients are expected to be diagnosed in the future, developing a genetic intervention can become very impactful. The prime example for such a situation is spinal muscular atrophy, for which SMA type I usually progresses so rapidly that, without treatment, it leads to death within the first two years of age.⁹⁶ However, with multiple genetic interventions now available, alongside newborn screening for SMA in several countries, patients can be treated pre-symptomatically or at a very early disease stage, which has enabled their near-typical development.

2.5.2 Disease stages

Diseases can follow different patterns: some progress at a relatively constant rate, whether slow or rapid (discussed above); others show little to no progression over time; and some evolve in stages, with periods of stability alternating with phases of more rapid change. Disease stages are clinically defined phases in the natural history of a disorder, distinguished by specific pathological or phenotypic features. Understanding the different phases and their typical duration is part of obtaining natural history data. The way the different stages present and how they follow each other is specific for each disease. For example, a disease may present with a plateau or stagnation phase followed by an improvement later in life (e.g. *FOXP1* syndrome).⁹⁷ A disease may also present as rather mild in early phases or can be temporarily stagnant and then rapidly progress (e.g. Beta-propeller Protein-associated Neurodegeneration (BPAN)).⁹⁸ In theory, diseases with various stages

can be eligible for therapy development. For generalized developments, understanding the different stages will help in determining the optimal therapeutic window of opportunity (see below). Evaluating disease stages is even more important for individual therapy developments as the stage of the disease will determine if and what type of therapeutic benefit can be expected.

2.5.3 Developmental milestones

Certain developmental milestones (motor and cognitive skills) can only be reached in defined developmental windows. An example of this is found for Angelman Syndrome (OMIM #105830), which is caused by loss of *UBE3A* expression in neurons. In mice, the loss of the *Ube3a* expression in adulthood (after the developmental milestones have been reached) did result in most behavioral phenotypes associated with Angelman Syndrome,⁹⁹ while reinstatement of *Ube3a* expression in adulthood (after the developmental milestones had been missed) did not rescue most behavioral phenotypes associated with Angelman Syndrome.¹⁰⁰

Therefore, similarly to how slowing down progression can serve as a clinical outcome measure, achieving developmental milestones can serve as an outcome measure, such as gaining motor skills or cognitive development. The size and shape of the developmental windows, which overlaps with the therapeutic window of opportunity, can complicate timely development (for milestones with short windows), or efficacy assessments (for milestones with large windows).

2.5.4 Therapeutic Window of Opportunity

Taken together, the optimal time point of intervention and timeframe during which an intervention can still lead to a clinical benefit is influenced by a multitude of factors. A therapeutic window of opportunity thus can present in different shapes.

For some diseases, therapeutic efficacy is confined to a narrow window, beyond which irreversible cellular loss precludes meaningful clinical benefit. In other diseases, this window progressively narrows as pathology accumulates, leading to diminishing—though not absent—effects over time. Accordingly, early intervention, ideally pre-symptomatic, is generally preferred to maximize clinical benefit and quality of life. The window and its shape (well-defined or narrowing with time) are determined by different criteria, such as developmental requirements for functional protein expression from a target gene (or even a specific gene transcript), or from irreversible tissue degeneration caused by pathogenic variants.^{100,101} While natural history studies provide important insights, the most definitive understanding often comes from clinical experience, where treatment outcomes can be directly correlated with the timing of intervention.

There are also disease manifestations that cannot be targeted by a (postnatal) genetic therapy, as the window has closed during early prenatal development. For example, structural anomalies that reflect abnormal development or tissue damage due to very fast progressing diseases in the embryonic period cannot be reversed. Consequently, any downstream symptoms of such damage, like seizures, are suboptimal therapeutic targets. While there are early animal studies to treat certain disorders *in utero* to avoid such damage, we will not discuss these considerations in detail here.¹⁰²

Recent developments in prenatal and newborn screening have enabled presymptomatic diagnosis, allowing early treatment initiation for disorders such as spinal muscular atrophy (SMA)

and metachromatic leukodystrophy (MLD).¹⁰³ At present, inclusion of a gene in such a screening requires a well-established gene–disease association, clear clinical actionability, and sufficient evidence supporting the pathogenic mechanism of identified variants to guide therapeutic strategy.¹⁰⁴ Expanding these programs to include additional treatable conditions or actionable variants could enable diagnosis prior to symptom onset, and with that effectively extend the therapeutic window by months to years—an important advantage for diseases in which opportunities for intervention after clinical presentation are limited.

2.6 Benefit-risk assessments

Before any therapy development can commence, the risks and potential benefits of a genetic intervention must be carefully considered and weighed. Benefit-risk assessments have to be made for every disease or gene and the chosen therapeutic intervention individually.

This assessment needs to consider the potential clinical benefit of a given therapy for an individual or group of patients in light of the current and expected disease burden as the disease progresses. Assessing the clinical benefit will take into account the different points addressed above, such as treatable symptoms, suitable clinical outcome measures, and the window of opportunity. A benefit-risk assessment also includes carefully considering other available therapeutic options, including other genetic interventions, and what could reasonably be achieved with the currently best clinical management and care, as well as which risks these options themselves bear.

Risks will depend on the therapeutic modality and the chosen delivery system. This includes, for example, assessing potential immunotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, or long-term carcinogenesis. It also includes assessing any potential off-target effects the drugs might have within the target tissue or in other, unrelated tissues to which the drug will be delivered. As DNA-based strategies are typically irreversible, compared to the effects of RNA-based interventions, which wear off over time, evaluating potential off-target effects is even more crucial. On the other hand, RNA-based therapies require recurrent administration, thereby potentially adding to treatment burden, especially if adverse effects are expected from the delivery systems.

Consequently, for individualized therapies and small groups of patients, market-approved chemistries and delivery routes are chosen as the safety profiles are well understood. For therapeutic modalities where risks are not yet fully understood, and some uncertainties still exist, the benefit-risk assessments need to be performed with additional caution. This also includes counselling the patients and families in advance, addressing potential risks and uncertainties clearly and transparently. As we better understand therapeutic safety profiles following increased clinical implementation, we expect this to inform the risk-benefit assessments in the future.

We recommend conducting the benefit-risk assessment together with the clinical team, ethics committee, the regulators (where applicable), and thorough discussion with patients and/or caretakers/families.

In current practice, benefit–risk assessment for individual genetic therapies is largely qualitative and based on case-by-case, multidisciplinary discussions. Ideally, a standardized, systematic, and reproducible process should be used for these assessments across institutions and development trajectories.

At a broader level, regulatory agencies have recently begun using structured benefit–risk assessment frameworks for medicinal products seeking market authorization.¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁷ However, systematic approaches specific to genetic medicines are only beginning to emerge and are not yet widely implemented but urgently needed.¹⁰⁸⁻¹¹²

3. Practical considerations

In addition to the above-discussed considerations, there are a few more practical considerations that should be made before deciding whether a gene or disease is currently eligible for therapeutic development.

3.1 Available therapies

Before developing a new genetic therapy for an individual or group of patients, one must consider what genetic and non-genetic therapeutic options are already available or are undergoing a clinical trial. This ranges from variant-specific therapeutic options that can be used in another patient with an identical genetic variant, to gene-specific therapeutic options suitable for all patients that have pathogenic variants in the same gene with the same pathomechanism. It also includes non-genetic therapies like small molecules identified via drug-repurposing or off-label use of available medicines. To facilitate the reapplication of genetic therapeutics, the N=1 Collaborative has established the N1C Gene Registry. This registry contains an overview of variants and genes for which genetic therapeutics are in use or under development in either an N=1 or a commercialized setting. The registry aims to support awareness and accelerate the development of treatments for ultra-rare conditions by increasing transparency and reducing duplicate efforts (<https://generegistry.n1collaborative.org/index.html>). Similarly, the non-profit n-Lorem provides an overview of their available individualized ASO therapies on their website (<https://www.nlorem.org/patients/active-gene-programs/>).

Additionally, other databases are available that provide an overview of available therapies for rare diseases, including RX Genes (<https://www.rx-genes.com/>) and the TreatabolomeDB (<https://treatabolome.org>) and RxMatcher (<https://rxmatcher.org/>), a platform for clinicians and researchers to share their experiences using off-label drug treatments in genetic diseases. There is also a Gene Therapy Trial Browser available, providing an overview of ongoing clinical trials (<https://scge.mcw.edu/platform/data/search/ClinicalTrial>).

It is important to note that for most diseases, no disease-modifying and targeted therapy is available yet. We still recommend performing a literature search to understand if therapeutic options have already been explored pre-clinically, and whether considerations regarding potential therapeutic interventions have been discussed and reported. This can help to understand what others have tried and either succeeded or failed at, and will support discussions on therapeutic suitability.

3.2 Pre-clinical development necessities

Many of the above-mentioned considerations are theoretical, and in theory, a genetic intervention may be possible for many diseases. However, given current limitations (e.g. effective delivery to a target tissue), a therapy might not be clinically feasible. Here, we provide additional criteria to consider before therapeutic development becomes clinically feasible.

Feasibility of a therapeutic development depends on the availability of preclinical tools, such as disease-relevant *in vitro* and, where applicable, *in vivo* models, reliable phenotypic readouts, and scalable platforms for testing therapeutic efficacy. Without these foundational elements, even technically actionable findings may remain clinically out of reach.

This evaluation should first include making an inventory of available, disease-relevant preclinical models, such as animal models or 2D/3D cell-based disease-modelling systems in which initial testing can be performed. This means models in which the genes of interest are sufficiently expressed, and a phenotype has been established. This inventory should also contain information on whether the models can be used to study efficacy, off-target effects and/or assess toxicity. It further needs to be determined on what level – DNA, RNA, protein or signaling pathway – changes and efficacy should be measured, and whether respective functional readouts are currently available or can be developed in a timely manner. In the context of specific assays and read-outs, it is important to assess whether appropriate and specific probes/antibodies for such readouts exist. If no models or developed assays are published or commercially available, this will drastically increase the work and time required for validation and preclinical testing of a genetic therapy.

Additionally, modality-specific considerations need to be made. For gene editing approaches, for example, the percentage of required editing is helpful to understand, yet it is still beneficial to see a functional effect in the model system, as it is not always known whether a specific degree of change is sufficient to rescue phenotypes. Thus, such model systems should be available. For gene replacement approaches, it will be important to not only detect the replaced gene but also see functional effects to measure if an increase in gene product can do any harm. For RNA therapies, one has to consider whether it is sufficient to show efficacy on mRNA level. This might be suitable for splice-correction approaches using ASOs, but not for strategies using exon skipping for knockdown approaches.

Overall, one should investigate what amount/type of preclinical change on protein level (upregulation or downregulation) is considered beneficial when applied clinically. It is important to be aware in this context that changes found in a preclinical model do not necessarily mean the same level of effect will be found clinically.^{113,114}

Notably, while out of scope for the initial assessment of eligibility, if during the pre-clinical development disease-relevant phenotypes cannot be reversed in an established model system, it should be considered if the disease is not reversible in humans also and therefore not treatable, or if imperfections in a model system (such as species differences or cell model maturity) can explain this lack of rescue. Nonetheless, a lack of phenotypic reversal in a disease model should be approached with caution.

In all cases, understanding off-target effects is important to successfully develop a genetic therapy. For the initial eligibility assessment, one should consider the different cell types and tissues that are most likely to be exposed to the therapeutic based on the delivery approach (consider

pharmacokinetics). This includes understanding which genes are potential off-targets of the therapeutic, and the safety concerns related to targeting those genes. For potential off-targets, not only the expression profile in the targeted tissues, but also developmental changes in expression profile of these off-targets can help assess the risk involved with developing a therapy. This risk might be different for children and adults. For the choice of a model system, it is important to consider whether the effect on predicted off-target genes can accurately be assessed.

Overall, as part of the eligibility assessment, one must take into account how preclinical success can be measured and demonstrated depending on the therapeutic approach, target tissue, and clinical aims. For certain diseases, this may mean that further preclinical modeling and design is required prior to therapeutic development.

3.3 Individualized therapy vs. generalized therapy

When considering therapeutic development, it is crucial to understand who will receive the therapy. For individualized therapies, different aspects and criteria need to be taken into account compared to therapy developments for entire patient populations. Some of these discussion points were addressed earlier, but we emphasize relevant takeaways here once more.

For individualized therapy, the focus is on the affected individual. Notably, while usually not the goal, it is possible for genetic therapies developed in an individualized setting to transition to use for a group of patients sharing the same genetic variant or sharing a SNP in cis with a pathogenic variant when considering allele-selective knockdown approaches. One example of an individualized, variant-specific therapy that is currently administered to two patients is the ASO atipeksen.¹¹⁵

In personalized drug development, understanding of the variant's underlying pathomechanism is required to guide the selection of the most appropriate therapeutic strategy for a given individual. This also necessitates evaluation of the individual's therapeutic window of opportunity, including understanding what clinical function is preservable and how the quality of life can be improved, relevant clinical targets, and the timelines associated with developing and administering different therapeutic modalities. All these considerations and discussions have to be made together with the individual and their caretakers. The development trajectory will further include several time points where the patient and their therapeutic eligibility will be assessed before the next development steps are taken. Overall, the case for or against an individualized therapy depends on whether the expected clinical benefit outweighs both the risks of the intervention and the residual uncertainty associated with limited safety and efficacy evidence. As such, the therapy development for such individual cases is vastly different from that for a commercial drug.¹¹⁶

For therapeutic developments for groups of patients, it is necessary to determine what would be the best therapeutic strategy for the full cohort. That means the general pathomechanism of the disease, the variant spectrum, and natural history, *i.e.* looking into the most common, prevalent, and severe symptoms and how these can be targeted, is of relevance. Considerations on the therapeutic window also differ, as the therapy can, in theory, be available even pre-symptomatically. As these developments, often with the aim of reaching market authorization, require additional preclinical evidence, more extensive safety testing, and clinical trials, they will be much more expensive. To be

able to bridge the gap from a promising preclinical therapeutic candidate to an actual therapy used in clinic, it is necessary to be aware the funding needs to be secured, which will often include securing patents and intellectual property rights at an early stage.

Overall, a clear understanding of the key requirements in genetic therapy development can support the identification of eligible genes and hereditary diseases, inform the selection of appropriate therapeutic strategies, and guide the progression from preclinical research to clinical implementation.

References

1. Pandey R, Brennan NF, Trachana K, et al. A meta-analysis of diagnostic yield and clinical utility of genome and exome sequencing in pediatric rare and undiagnosed genetic diseases. *Genet Med*. Jun 2025;27(6):101398. doi:10.1016/j.gim.2025.101398
2. Yepez VA, Gusic M, Kopajtich R, et al. Clinical implementation of RNA sequencing for Mendelian disease diagnostics. *Genome Med*. Apr 5 2022;14(1):38. doi:10.1186/s13073-022-01019-9
3. Wright CF, McRae JF, Clayton S, et al. Making new genetic diagnoses with old data: iterative reanalysis and reporting from genome-wide data in 1,133 families with developmental disorders. *Genet Med*. Oct 2018;20(10):1216-1223. doi:10.1038/gim.2017.246
4. Yang Y, Muzny DM, Reid JG, et al. Clinical whole-exome sequencing for the diagnosis of mendelian disorders. *N Engl J Med*. Oct 17 2013;369(16):1502-11. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1306555
5. Farwell KD, Shahmirzadi L, El-Khechen D, et al. Enhanced utility of family-centered diagnostic exome sequencing with inheritance model-based analysis: results from 500 unselected families with undiagnosed genetic conditions. *Genet Med*. Jul 2015;17(7):578-86. doi:10.1038/gim.2014.154
6. Zhao S, Macakova K, Sinson JC, et al. Clinical validation of RNA sequencing for Mendelian disorder diagnostics. *Am J Hum Genet*. Apr 3 2025;112(4):779-792. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2025.02.006
7. Li S, Zhao S, Sinson JC, et al. The clinical utility and diagnostic implementation of human subject cell transdifferentiation followed by RNA sequencing. *Am J Hum Genet*. May 2 2024;111(5):841-862. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2024.03.007
8. Richards S, Aziz N, Bale S, et al. Standards and guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants: a joint consensus recommendation of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics and the Association for Molecular Pathology. *Genet Med*. May 2015;17(5):405-24. doi:10.1038/gim.2015.30
9. Laugwitz L, Santhanakumaran V, Spieker M, et al. Extremely low arylsulfatase A enzyme activity does not necessarily cause symptoms: A long-term follow-up and review of the literature. *JIMD Rep*. Jul 2022;63(4):292-302. doi:10.1002/jmd2.12293
10. Rehm HL, Berg JS, Brooks LD, et al. ClinGen--the Clinical Genome Resource. *N Engl J Med*. Jun 4 2015;372(23):2235-42. doi:10.1056/NEJMSr1406261
11. Amberger JS, Bocchini CA, Schiettecatte F, Scott AF, Hamosh A. OMIM.org: Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM(R)), an online catalog of human genes and genetic disorders. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Jan 2015;43(Database issue):D789-98. doi:10.1093/nar/gku1205
12. Weinreich SS, Mangon R, Sikkens JJ, Teeuw ME, Cornel MC. Orphanet: a European database for rare diseases. *Ned Tijdschr Geneesk*. Mar 1 2008;152(9):518-9.
13. *GeneReviews*. 2026/01/01 ed. University of Washington; 1993-2026.

14. Hunt SE, Lemos D, Pericherla SR, et al. Gene2Phenotype: A Database of Structured Human Monogenic Diseases and Pathomechanisms. *J Mol Biol.* Mar 26 2026;169768. doi:10.1016/j.jmb.2026.169768
15. DiStefano N, Cooper JN, Elisha DH, et al. Decoding SCN2A Variants: Bridging Genetics and Phenotypes in Autism Spectrum Disorder. *J Clin Med.* May 28 2025;14(11)doi:10.3390/jcm14113790
16. Strande NT, Riggs ER, Buchanan AH, et al. Evaluating the Clinical Validity of Gene-Disease Associations: An Evidence-Based Framework Developed by the Clinical Genome Resource. *Am J Hum Genet.* Jun 1 2017;100(6):895-906. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2017.04.015
17. Zonic E, Ferreira M, Pardo LM, et al. Systematic gene-disease relationship (GDR) curation unveils 61 gene-disease associations and highlights the impact on genetic testing. *Genet Med Open.* 2023;1(1):100833. doi:10.1016/j.gimo.2023.100833
18. Stark Z, Byrne AB, Sampson MG, Lennon R, Mallett AJ. A guide to gene-disease relationships in nephrology. *Nat Rev Nephrol.* Feb 2025;21(2):115-126. doi:10.1038/s41581-024-00900-7
19. Cipriani V, Vestito L, Magavern EF, et al. Rare disease gene association discovery in the 100,000 Genomes Project. *Nature.* Feb 26 2025;doi:10.1038/s41586-025-08623-w
20. Gene-Disease Validity Curation. Clinical Genome Resource. Accessed May 8, 2026. <https://clinicalgenome.org/curation-activities/gene-disease-validity/>
21. Santen GWE, Leitch HG, Cobben J. Gene-disease relationship evidence: A clinical perspective focusing on ultra-rare diseases. *Hum Mutat.* Aug 2022;43(8):1082-1088. doi:10.1002/humu.24367
22. Yates TM, Ansari M, Thompson L, et al. Curating genomic disease-gene relationships with Gene2Phenotype (G2P). *Genome Med.* Nov 6 2024;16(1):127. doi:10.1186/s13073-024-01398-1
23. Kingdom R, Wright CF. Incomplete Penetrance and Variable Expressivity: From Clinical Studies to Population Cohorts. *Front Genet.* 2022;13:920390. doi:10.3389/fgene.2022.920390
24. Backwell L, Marsh JA. Diverse Molecular Mechanisms Underlying Pathogenic Protein Mutations: Beyond the Loss-of-Function Paradigm. *Annu Rev Genomics Hum Genet.* Aug 31 2022;23:475-498. doi:10.1146/annurev-genom-111221-103208
25. Bartha I, di Iulio J, Venter JC, Telenti A. Human gene essentiality. *Nat Rev Genet.* Jan 2018;19(1):51-62. doi:10.1038/nrg.2017.75
26. Ghazizadeh S, Kalish RS, Taichman LB. Immune-mediated loss of transgene expression in skin: implications for cutaneous gene therapy. *Mol Ther.* Mar 2003;7(3):296-303. doi:10.1016/s1525-0016(03)00013-3
27. Hanemann CO, Muller HW. Pathogenesis of Charcot-Marie-Tooth 1A (CMT1A) neuropathy. *Trends Neurosci.* Jul 1998;21(7):282-6. doi:10.1016/s0166-2236(97)01222-8
28. Ueyama T, Ninoyu Y, Nishio SY, et al. Constitutive activation of DIA1 (DIAPH1) via C-terminal truncation causes human sensorineural hearing loss. *EMBO Mol Med.* Nov 2016;8(11):1310-1324. doi:10.15252/emmm.201606609
29. Baron DM, Fenton AR, Saez-Atienzar S, et al. ALS-associated KIF5A mutations abolish autoinhibition resulting in a toxic gain of function. *Cell Rep.* Apr 5 2022;39(1):110598. doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2022.110598
30. Maloney RC, Zhang M, Jang H, Nussinov R. The mechanism of activation of monomeric B-Raf V600E. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J.* 2021;19:3349-3363. doi:10.1016/j.csbj.2021.06.007
31. Cuesta-Munoz AL, Huopio H, Otonkoski T, et al. Severe persistent hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia due to a de novo glucokinase mutation. *Diabetes.* Aug 2004;53(8):2164-8. doi:10.2337/diabetes.53.8.2164

32. Tedesco B, Vendredy L, Adriaenssens E, et al. HSPB8 frameshift mutant aggregates weaken chaperone-assisted selective autophagy in neuromyopathies. *Autophagy*. Aug 2023;19(8):2217-2239. doi:10.1080/15548627.2023.2179780
33. Sulkowski PL, Corso CD, Robinson ND, et al. 2-Hydroxyglutarate produced by neomorphic IDH mutations suppresses homologous recombination and induces PARP inhibitor sensitivity. *Sci Transl Med*. Feb 1 2017;9(375)doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.aal2463
34. Veitia RA. Exploring the molecular etiology of dominant-negative mutations. *Plant Cell*. Dec 2007;19(12):3843-51. doi:10.1105/tpc.107.055053
35. Quinodoz M, Peter VG, Cisarova K, et al. Analysis of missense variants in the human genome reveals widespread gene-specific clustering and improves prediction of pathogenicity. *Am J Hum Genet*. Mar 3 2022;109(3):457-470. doi:10.1016/j.ajhg.2022.01.006
36. Sinha Ray S, Dutta D, Dennys C, et al. Mechanisms of IRF2BPL-related disorders and identification of a potential therapeutic strategy. *Cell Rep*. Dec 6 2022;41(10):111751. doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2022.111751
37. Carvill GL, Matheny T, Hesselberth J, Demarest S. Haploinsufficiency, Dominant Negative, and Gain-of-Function Mechanisms in Epilepsy: Matching Therapeutic Approach to the Pathophysiology. *Neurotherapeutics*. Jul 2021;18(3):1500-1514. doi:10.1007/s13311-021-01137-z
38. RTW Foundation Works with Elly's Team to Achieve One of the Fastest Gene Therapy Development Efforts in History Setting a New Precedent for Ultra-Rare Disease Treatment. RTW Foundation. Accessed May 8, 2026. <https://www.rtwf.org/news-and-resources/news/rtw-foundation-works-with-ellys-team-to-achieve-one-of-the-fastest-gene-therapy-development-efforts-in-history-setting-a-new-precedent-for-ultra-rare-disease-treatment/>
39. O'Reilly M, Palfi A, Chadderton N, et al. RNA interference-mediated suppression and replacement of human rhodopsin in vivo. *Am J Hum Genet*. Jul 2007;81(1):127-35. doi:10.1086/519025
40. Strings-Ufombah V, Malerba A, Kao SC, et al. BB-301: a silence and replace AAV-based vector for the treatment of oculopharyngeal muscular dystrophy. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. Jun 4 2021;24:67-78. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2021.02.017
41. Clinical Trial of BB-301. National Library of Medicine. Accessed May 8, 2026. ClinicalTrials.gov ID NCT06185673
42. Asadollahi R, Delvendahl I, Muff R, et al. Pathogenic SCN2A variants cause early-stage dysfunction in patient-derived neurons. *Hum Mol Genet*. Jun 19 2023;32(13):2192-2204. doi:10.1093/hmg/ddad048
43. Kim-McManus O, Goddard P, Olsson S, et al. Scaling haplo-specific antisense oligonucleotides from N-of-1 to broad use in genetic disease populations by diplotyping. *medRxiv*. 2026:2026.01.28.26345012. doi:10.64898/2026.01.28.26345012
44. Kim-McManus O, Mignon L, Douville J, et al. Individualized Antisense Oligonucleotides for SCN2A Related Developmental Epileptic Encephalopathy. *Research Square (PREPRINT)*. 18 October 2025 2025;doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-7841195/v1
45. Toydemir RM, Brassington AE, Bayrak-Toydemir P, et al. A novel mutation in FGFR3 causes camptodactyly, tall stature, and hearing loss (CATSHL) syndrome. *Am J Hum Genet*. Nov 2006;79(5):935-41. doi:10.1086/508433
46. Baker MD, Nassar MA. Painful and painless mutations of SCN9A and SCN11A voltage-gated sodium channels. *Pflugers Arch*. Jul 2020;472(7):865-880. doi:10.1007/s00424-020-02419-9
47. Zschocke J, Byers PH, Wilkie AOM. Mendelian inheritance revisited: dominance and recessiveness in medical genetics. *Nat Rev Genet*. Jul 2023;24(7):442-463. doi:10.1038/s41576-023-00574-0

48. Lek M, Karczewski KJ, Minikel EV, et al. Analysis of protein-coding genetic variation in 60,706 humans. *Nature*. Aug 18 2016;536(7616):285-91. doi:10.1038/nature19057
49. Karczewski KJ, Francioli LC, Tiao G, et al. The mutational constraint spectrum quantified from variation in 141,456 humans. *Nature*. May 2020;581(7809):434-443. doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2308-7
50. Collins RL, Glessner JT, Porcu E, et al. A cross-disorder dosage sensitivity map of the human genome. *Cell*. Aug 4 2022;185(16):3041-3055 e25. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2022.06.036
51. Dosage Sensitivity. Clinical Genome Resource. Accessed February 13, 2026. <https://search.clinicalgenome.org/kb/gene-dosage?page=1&size=25&search=>
52. ClinGen Dosage Sensitivity Data Entry Process: Standard Operating Procedure. The Clinical Genome Resource Dosage Sensitivity Working Group. Accessed February 13, 2026. https://www.clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/6492/dosage_sop-jira.pdf
53. Dosage Sensitivity Track Settings. UCSC Genome Browser. Accessed February 13, 2026. <https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg38&position=default&g=dosageSensitivity>
54. Lauffer MC, van Roon-Mom W, Aartsma-Rus A, Collaborative N. Possibilities and limitations of antisense oligonucleotide therapies for the treatment of monogenic disorders. *Commun Med (Lond)*. Jan 5 2024;4(1):6. doi:10.1038/s43856-023-00419-1
55. Cerillo JL, Parmar M, Tofersen. Jan 2025;doi:NBK594270
56. Joubran E, Nguyen H, Inotersen. Jan 2025;doi:NBK578206
57. Ziegler A, Carroll J, Bain JM, et al. Antisense oligonucleotide therapy in an individual with KIF1A-associated neurological disorder. *Nat Med*. Oct 2024;30(10):2782-2786. doi:10.1038/s41591-024-03197-y
58. Mueller C, Berry JD, McKenna-Yasek DM, et al. SOD1 Suppression with Adeno-Associated Virus and MicroRNA in Familial ALS. *N Engl J Med*. Jul 9 2020;383(2):151-158. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2005056
59. Clinical Trials of YOLT-101. National Library of Medicine. Accessed February 13, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06458010>
60. Wan P, Tang S, Lin D, et al. In vivo base editing gene therapy for heterozygous familial hypercholesterolemia: a phase 1 trial. *Nat Med*. Mar 2026;32(3):1045-1051. doi:10.1038/s41591-026-04254-4
61. Iwamoto N, Liu Y, Frank-Kamenetsky M, et al. Preclinical evaluation of stereopure antisense oligonucleotides for allele-selective lowering of mutant HTT. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. Sep 10 2024;35(3):102246. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2024.102246
62. McColgan P, Thobhani A, Boak L, et al. Tominersen in Adults with Manifest Huntington's Disease. *N Engl J Med*. Dec 7 2023;389(23):2203-2205. doi:10.1056/NEJMc2300400
63. Li M, Jancovski N, Jafar-Nejad P, et al. Antisense oligonucleotide therapy reduces seizures and extends life span in an SCN2A gain-of-function epilepsy model. *J Clin Invest*. Dec 1 2021;131(23)doi:10.1172/JCI152079
64. Wagnon JL, Barker BS, Ottolini M, et al. Loss-of-function variants of SCN8A in intellectual disability without seizures. *Neurol Genet*. Aug 2017;3(4):e170. doi:10.1212/NXG.0000000000000170
65. Sahly AN, Sierra-Marquez J, Bungert-Plumke S, et al. Genotype-phenotype correlation in CLCN4-related developmental and epileptic encephalopathy. *Hum Genet*. May 2024;143(5):667-681. doi:10.1007/s00439-024-02668-z
66. Lim KH, Han Z, Jeon HY, et al. Antisense oligonucleotide modulation of non-productive alternative splicing upregulates gene expression. *Nat Commun*. Jul 9 2020;11(1):3501. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-17093-9

67. Egli M, Manoharan M. Chemistry, structure and function of approved oligonucleotide therapeutics. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Apr 11 2023;51(6):2529-2573. doi:10.1093/nar/gkad067
68. Day JW, Finkel RS, Chiriboga CA, et al. Onasemnogene abeparvovec gene therapy for symptomatic infantile-onset spinal muscular atrophy in patients with two copies of SMN2 (STR1VE): an open-label, single-arm, multicentre, phase 3 trial. *Lancet Neurol.* Apr 2021;20(4):284-293. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00001-6
69. Huang X, Zhou C, Tian M, et al. Overexpressing wild-type gamma2 subunits rescued the seizure phenotype in Gabrg2(+Q390X) Dravet syndrome mice. *Epilepsia.* Aug 2017;58(8):1451-1461. doi:10.1111/epi.13810
70. Laundos TL, Li S, Cheang E, De Santis R, Piccolo FM, Brivanlou AH. Huntingtin CAG-expansion mutation results in a dominant negative effect. *Front Cell Dev Biol.* 2023;11:1252521. doi:10.3389/fcell.2023.1252521
71. Aartsma-Rus A, Straub V, Hemmings R, et al. Development of Exon Skipping Therapies for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy: A Critical Review and a Perspective on the Outstanding Issues. *Nucleic Acid Ther.* Oct 2017;27(5):251-259. doi:10.1089/nat.2017.0682
72. Palmer EE, Howell K, Scheffer IE. Natural History Studies and Clinical Trial Readiness for Genetic Developmental and Epileptic Encephalopathies. *Neurotherapeutics.* Jul 2021;18(3):1432-1444. doi:10.1007/s13311-021-01133-3
73. The Genotype-Tissue Expression Project. <https://gtexportal.org/home/>
74. Uhlen M, Fagerberg L, Hallstrom BM, et al. Proteomics. Tissue-based map of the human proteome. *Science.* Jan 23 2015;347(6220):1260419. doi:10.1126/science.1260419
75. Hekselman I, Vital A, Ziv-Agam M, Kerber L, Yairi I, Yeger-Lotem E. Affected cell types for hundreds of Mendelian diseases revealed by analysis of human and mouse single-cell data. *Elife.* Jan 10 2024;13doi:10.7554/eLife.84613
76. Al Hafid N, Christodoulou J. Phenylketonuria: a review of current and future treatments. *Transl Pediatr.* Oct 2015;4(4):304-17. doi:10.3978/j.issn.2224-4336.2015.10.07
77. Fitzgerald K, White S, Borodovsky A, et al. A Highly Durable RNAi Therapeutic Inhibitor of PCSK9. *N Engl J Med.* Jan 5 2017;376(1):41-51. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1609243
78. Hammond SM, Aartsma-Rus A, Alves S, et al. Delivery of oligonucleotide-based therapeutics: challenges and opportunities. *EMBO Mol Med.* Apr 9 2021;13(4):e13243. doi:10.15252/emmm.202013243
79. Wang JH, Gessler DJ, Zhan W, Gallagher TL, Gao G. Adeno-associated virus as a delivery vector for gene therapy of human diseases. *Signal Transduct Target Ther.* Apr 3 2024;9(1):78. doi:10.1038/s41392-024-01780-w
80. Lino CA, Harper JC, Carney JP, Timlin JA. Delivering CRISPR: a review of the challenges and approaches. *Drug Deliv.* Nov 2018;25(1):1234-1257. doi:10.1080/10717544.2018.1474964
81. Raguram A, Banskota S, Liu DR. Therapeutic in vivo delivery of gene editing agents. *Cell.* Jul 21 2022;185(15):2806-2827. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2022.03.045
82. Matsuda S, Keiser K, Nair JK, et al. siRNA conjugates carrying sequentially assembled trivalent N-acetylgalactosamine linked through nucleosides elicit robust gene silencing in vivo in hepatocytes. *ACS Chem Biol.* May 15 2015;10(5):1181-7. doi:10.1021/cb501028c
83. Clinical Trials of WWE-006. National Library of Medicine. Accessed February 16, 2026. <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06405633>
84. Weeden T, Picariello T, Quinn B, et al. FORCE platform overcomes barriers of oligonucleotide delivery to muscle and corrects myotonic dystrophy features in preclinical models. *Commun Med (Lond).* Jan 18 2025;5(1):22. doi:10.1038/s43856-025-00733-w

85. Ostergaard ME, Carrer M, Anderson BA, et al. Conjugation to a transferrin receptor 1-binding Bicycle peptide enhances ASO and siRNA potency in skeletal and cardiac muscles. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Apr 10 2025;53(7)doi:10.1093/nar/gkaf270
86. Tsuboi T, Hattori K, Ishimoto T, et al. In vivo efficacy and safety of systemically administered serinol nucleic acid-modified antisense oligonucleotides in mouse kidney. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids.* Mar 11 2025;36(1):102387. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2024.102387
87. Koeberl D, Schulze A, Sondheimer N, et al. Publisher Correction: Interim analyses of a first-in-human phase 1/2 mRNA trial for propionic acidaemia. *Nature.* Jun 2024;630(8017):E13. doi:10.1038/s41586-024-07646-z
88. Rice AM, Li Y, Donnelly P, McLysaght A. Evolution of Dosage-Sensitive Genes by Tissue-Restricted Expression Changes. *Genome Biol Evol.* Jul 30 2025;17(8)doi:10.1093/gbe/evaf132
89. Hordeaux J, Buza EL, Jeffrey B, et al. MicroRNA-mediated inhibition of transgene expression reduces dorsal root ganglion toxicity by AAV vectors in primates. *Sci Transl Med.* Nov 11 2020;12(569)doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.aba9188
90. Al-Ghoul M, Valdes R, Jr. Fundamentals of pharmacology and applications in pharmacogenetics. *Clin Lab Med.* Dec 2008;28(4):485-97. doi:10.1016/j.cll.2008.07.001
91. IND Submissions for Individualized Antisense Oligonucleotide Drug Products: Administrative and Procedural Recommendations (Guidance for Sponsor-Investigators). U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Food and Drug Administration, Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER). Accessed February 16, 2026. <https://www.fda.gov/media/144872/download>
92. Guerrini R, Conti V. Epileptic encephalopathies and progressive neurodegeneration. *Rev Neurol (Paris).* May 2024;180(5):363-367. doi:10.1016/j.neurol.2024.03.004
93. Hipp JF, Bacino CA, Bird LM, et al. The UBE3A-ATS antisense oligonucleotide rugonersen in children with Angelman syndrome: a phase 1 trial. *Nat Med.* Sep 2025;31(9):2936-2945. doi:10.1038/s41591-025-03784-7
94. Kim-McManus O, Gleeson JG, Mignon L, et al. A framework for N-of-1 trials of individualized gene-targeted therapies for genetic diseases. *Nat Commun.* Nov 12 2024;15(1):9802. doi:10.1038/s41467-024-54077-5
95. Reilly MM, Herrmann DN, Pareyson D, et al. Trials for Slowly Progressive Neurogenetic Diseases Need Surrogate Endpoints. *Ann Neurol.* May 2023;93(5):906-910. doi:10.1002/ana.26633
96. Mercuri E, Sumner CJ, Muntoni F, Darras BT, Finkel RS. Spinal muscular atrophy. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.* Aug 4 2022;8(1):52. doi:10.1038/s41572-022-00380-8
97. Rappold G, Siper P, Kostic A, et al. FOXP1 Syndrome. *GeneReviews.* 2023/09/21 ed. 1993.
98. Gregory A, Kurian MA, Wilson J, Hayflick S. Neurodegeneration with Brain Iron Accumulation Disorders Overview. *GeneReviews.* 2025/03/06 ed. 1993.
99. Sonzogni M, Hakonen J, Bernabe Kleijn M, et al. Delayed loss of UBE3A reduces the expression of Angelman syndrome-associated phenotypes. *Mol Autism.* 2019;10:23. doi:10.1186/s13229-019-0277-1
100. Silva-Santos S, van Woerden GM, Bruinsma CF, et al. Ube3a reinstatement identifies distinct developmental windows in a murine Angelman syndrome model. *J Clin Invest.* May 2015;125(5):2069-76. doi:10.1172/JCI80554
101. Yeo CJJ, Tizzano EF, Darras BT. Challenges and opportunities in spinal muscular atrophy therapeutics. *Lancet Neurol.* Feb 2024;23(2):205-218. doi:10.1016/S1474-4422(23)00419-2
102. Waddington SN, Peranteau WH, Rahim AA, et al. Fetal gene therapy. *J Inherit Metab Dis.* Jan 2024;47(1):192-210. doi:10.1002/jimd.12659

103. Parisi MA, Caggana M, Cohen JL, et al. When is the best time to screen and evaluate for treatable genetic disorders?: A lifespan perspective. *Am J Med Genet C Semin Med Genet*. Mar 2023;193(1):44-55. doi:10.1002/ajmg.c.32036
104. Betzler IR, Hempel M, Mutze U, et al. Comparative analysis of gene and disease selection in genomic newborn screening studies. *J Inherit Metab Dis*. Sep 2024;47(5):945-970. doi:10.1002/jimd.12750
105. McAuslane N, Leong J, Liberti L, Walker S. The Benefit-Risk Assessment of Medicines: Experience of a Consortium of Medium-Sized Regulatory Authorities. *Ther Innov Regul Sci*. Sep 2017;51(5):635-644. doi:10.1177/2168479017696260
106. Chisholm O, Sharry P, Phillips L. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis for Benefit-Risk Analysis by National Regulatory Authorities. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2021;8:820335. doi:10.3389/fmed.2021.820335
107. Benefit-Risk Assessment for New Drug and Biological Products: Guidance for Industry (2023).
108. Kurzinger ML, Douarin L, Uzun I, et al. Structured benefit-risk evaluation for medicinal products: review of quantitative benefit-risk assessment findings in the literature. *Ther Adv Drug Saf*. 2020;11:2042098620976951. doi:10.1177_2042098620976951
109. Danks L, Semete-Makokotlela B, Chuma D, et al. The value of a structured, systematic approach to benefit-risk assessment of medicines: A South African regulator case study. *Regul Toxicol Pharmacol*. Nov 2025;162:105893. doi:10.1016/j.yrtph.2025.105893
110. Bittlinger M, Hoffmann D, Sierawska AK, Mertz M, Schambach A, Strech D. Risk assessment in gene therapy and somatic genome-editing: An expert interview study. *Gene and Genome Editing*. 2022/12/01/ 2022;3-4:100011. doi:10.1016/j.ggedit.2022.100011
111. FDA Issues Draft Guidance on Genome Editing Safety Standards to Advance Gene Therapy Development (FDA) (2026).
112. Postapproval Methods to Capture Safety and Efficacy Data for Cell and Gene Therapy Products (FDA) (2025).
113. Christensen JK, Colletti N, Hooshfar S, et al. Translational and clinical development of therapeutic siRNA and ASOs: current industry practices, perspectives, and recommendations. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Sep 23 2025;53(18)doi:10.1093/nar/gkaf778
114. Oliver PL, Hill AC. Model selection in preclinical nucleic acid therapeutics research. *Commun Biol*. Feb 9 2026;9(1):200. doi:10.1038/s42003-026-09650-7
115. Kim J, Woo S, de Gusmao CM, et al. A framework for individualized splice-switching oligonucleotide therapy. *Nature*. Jul 2023;619(7971):828-836. doi:10.1038/s41586-023-06277-0
116. Jonker AH, Tataru EA, Graessner H, et al. The state-of-the-art of N-of-1 therapies and the IRDiRC N-of-1 development roadmap. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. Jan 2025;24(1):40-56. doi:10.1038/s41573-024-01059-3